

INITIATIVE, CREATIVITY AND CREATIVE APPROACH IN THE ACTIVITIES OF A LAWYER

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Annotation. This article examines the significance of initiative, creativity, and a creative approach in legal practice. It argues that successful lawyers must combine legal expertise with innovative thinking to solve complex problems, improve legal advocacy, enhance legal culture, and strengthen lawmaking and law enforcement. Creative lawyers play a decisive role in advancing national legal systems.

Key words: initiative, creativity, creative approach, lawyer, legal practice, law enforcement, legal advocacy, legal culture, lawmaking, professional competence

The Role and Importance of Personal Qualities in a Lawyer's Professional Activity.

Regardless of the field in which a lawyer practices, they will ultimately have to work with people and their problems and requests, and be able to address them. Whether they are a judge, a prosecutor, a defense attorney, a notary, a civil registry officer, an investigator, or a prison guard, their clients are real people, just like themselves.

Consequently, when people turn to lawyers, it turns out that their situation is radically different from that of others.

Human life is complex and contradictory, as the situations and problems they face defy any standard and vary greatly. Each issue requires an individual approach, and each problem requires its own solution.

So what do people expect from a lawyer first and foremost?

You've found the right answer: the problem needs to be resolved as quickly as possible and to their advantage. In this case, a person expects a lawyer to listen attentively, to care about their future, and to imagine themselves in their shoes.

While this applies to the expectations of the average person, business and organizational leaders demand that their lawyers perform their duties promptly, efficiently, and without question, ensuring that no further problems arise.

To meet all these requirements and desires and earn the respect of clients and managers, a lawyer must possess not only strong knowledge but also possess

such human qualities as initiative, determination, a creative approach to work and emerging problems, and a desire to create useful innovations.

Law enforcement and legal advocacy.

In other words, legal illiteracy leads to major problems in real life, giving rise to simple disagreements that can later escalate into serious conflicts. As a result, trivial everyday conflicts can lead to clashes between people, leading to serious crimes, including murder. However, legal illiteracy and ignorance of the law do not absolve a person from responsibility.

Therefore, one of the most important issues today is improving the legal literacy and legal culture of our citizens. In this case, propaganda and agitation are one of the most reliable and effective methods.

Frankly speaking, the truth is that the use of such expressions and concepts evokes a negative attitude and even irritation in many. In other words, the concept of "legal advocacy and agitation" conjures up images of a pointless event, where thirty to forty people gather in a room in 40-degree heat or extreme cold to listen to a boring one- or two-hour speech from someone staring at a piece of paper. Only at the end of the meeting can the chairperson boldly address the audience with the words, "Anyone with a question? Thank you to all the speakers." Only a truly creative and enterprising lawyer can accomplish the same task in such a way that, as a result of these efforts, everyone immediately understands everything, learning a lifelong lesson and acquiring vital knowledge and skills.

Modern technical and technological innovations make it possible to develop and apply numerous techniques and methods for more effectively assimilating the necessary knowledge and skills in people's legal awareness and fostering legal culture among the population. To achieve this, lawyers must apply a creative approach to their work, demonstrate initiative, and constantly devise new methods of advocacy to engage their audiences.

Initiative is an important factor in lawmaking. The concept of creativity: essence and meaning.

Creativity (creative approach) is the ability to create something new and unique, a mental process that leads to the development of artistic form, thought, ideas, and solutions [1].

From the definition of the concept, it follows that creativity, like initiative and a creative approach to work, cannot be merely an innate divine gift. Since creativity is a mental process, endless opportunities and means can arise to develop or enhance the human mind, to utilize its full potential.

Consequently, in a situation where each case requires an exclusively legal approach based on laws, codes, and established legal norms, the question logically arises regarding creativity: is it possible to "invent something new?" Wouldn't it lead to confusion and anarchy if every lawyer, be it a judge, prosecutor, attorney, or notary, were to apply some kind of innovation in every case under consideration? This is the whole point. When we talk about a lawyer's creativity, initiative, and creative approach to their work, we must never forget that all of this is strictly within the law and in accordance with it. Creativity, initiative, and a creative approach should never be the basis for breaking the law, circumventing it, or improperly applying it. Instead, they should serve to maximize the full, effective, and correct use of the opportunities afforded to the lawyer.

Creativity in the legal sphere means a creative, innovative, and unconventional approach to solving legal issues. Although this quality is evident in many lawyers, only those who have successfully demonstrated its value in practice stand out among representatives of this profession; such a specialist has a very large client base [2].

The reasons, place, and methods for manifesting a lawyer's creativity can be determined by their own discretion. It should be noted that the legislation of a number of countries, especially Uzbekistan, which for a long time lacked its own independent legal space, still contains many shortcomings and problems in the legal sphere, as well as many unresolved issues that require answers. It's impossible to find answers and resolve existing problems without a lawyer's creative approach.

This approach, as we noted above, although superficially similar, is in fact the only way to find the most reasonable solution in conflict situations and legal issues that don't intersect due to their subtleties, details, causes and consequences, their scope, and diversity. Both the client and their supervisor will be immensely grateful to a lawyer who has managed to find a solution to the problem through creativity and a creative approach.

The Role of Creativity in Law Enforcement.

Indeed, representatives of all professions should apply a creative approach to their work. Without such an approach, the development and improvement of any field is unthinkable.

Similarly, creativity, focused on attracting all kinds of innovations, is a characteristic feature of jurisprudence and cannot go unnoticed.

In a broad sense, this applies to lawmaking, legal doctrine, and the development of legal disciplines in the country, as well as the improvement of

legal practice [3]. Indeed, a creative approach, scientific and practical research in this area, with their influence and significance, lead to a significant improvement in the concept of law in the general sense.

When it comes to the specific field in which lawyers work and the accumulated problems, we can recall corruption, which is a serious obstacle to the development of our society, and the need to combat it in order to eradicate such an evil. It is well known that in a number of developed countries, such as Finland, Norway, Germany, New Zealand, and Singapore, this problem has long since ceased to be a problem, and its severity has significantly decreased [4]. So, how did these countries achieve this result, and at what cost were such vices as bribery, corruption, embezzlement of state funds, and the use of "connected" lawyers radically eliminated?

The answer to these questions is obvious: the fight against corruption by lawyers in these countries has yielded such positive results. They, first among themselves and then throughout society, have introduced new legal pathways, unexpected, effective methods, and mechanisms to eliminate this scourge.

Is it possible, based on the experience of other countries, to introduce new initiatives, combat methods, propaganda approaches, and other effective actions, taking into account the specificities of our real life, mentality, and national characteristics of our people? In our opinion, this is not only possible, but also extremely necessary!

Another thing to remember is that creative people who develop new ideas and apply unconventional approaches to solving problems are of constant interest to most employers. Qualities such as creativity and entrepreneurship occupy a special place among all the qualities required of specialists.

Today's pace of growth requires every country and its citizens to constantly strive for innovation, new ideas, initiative, and unexpected approaches and solutions. Delays in deadlines or significant backwardness, as a result, can lead to dependence on developed countries in all areas.

On the other hand, a modern lawyer must be a full participant in a rapidly changing world. Because almost every day in our country alone, many new laws and regulations are adopted, one replacing the other. It's no secret that this process is not smooth and flawless. Even among new laws, one can find duplicates, mutually canceling laws, and contradictory instructions. In raising, discussing, and effectively resolving these and similar issues, reforming our legislation and our national legal system, we need creative, inquisitive, and enterprising legal professionals, who are as vital to us as air and water. Therefore,

only creative lawyers, capable of boldly promoting new ideas and initiatives, will play a decisive role in our country's emergence as a leading legal power.

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